

e

Project Proposal

Open ODISSEI-eScience
Call 2022

netherlands
eSciencecenter

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This document contains explanatory text in italics. Please remove this text before submission.

Details of the applicant

Title	<i>Short title for this proposal. (Use this title as 'Title' in the EasyChair submission system).</i>
Lead applicant (LA)	<i>The name of the lead applicant. (Use this name as 'Author' in the EasyChair submission system)</i>
Position and Affiliation LA	<i>Used to determine the eligibility of the LA</i>
Year of PhD	<i>The year of the PhD degree of the LA.</i>
Email address LA	<i>This address will be used for all official communications</i>
Postal address LA	<i>For official correspondence with the LA</i>
Start date	no later than 31 December 2022
End date	no later than 1 September 2023
Requested RSE PMs	<i>3 person months (default and maximum)</i>

Research team

Name	Email	Position	Affiliation	Expertise	Availability for this project (hours/week)
<i>Lead Applicant</i>					
<i>Team member 1</i>					
<i>Team member 2</i>					
<i>Add/remove as many rows as required</i>					

Research Question (max 200 words)

Describe the research problem you are planning to work on and pose a concise research question following from that problem. Provide context for the importance of the problem being solved.

Planned work (max 200 words)

Describe your study. What do you expect the application of software to do for you?

Expected output (max 200 words)

Briefly describe the deliverables (for instance, title and topic) of a paper, blog post or code release.
Describe how this output will be used in your work and promoted after the project ends. (This can include knowledge development, software use, next steps in research, etc.)

Description of available data

For **each dataset** that you are considering using, please provide the following:

Dataset name	
Repository	<i>name of institute, library, etc.</i>
Short description	<i>max. 50 words</i>
Type of data	<i>text, images, audio, video, numerical, categorical, mixed etc.</i>
Format of the data	<i>html, txt, csv, pdf, etc.</i>
Metadata	<i>structure, standards used, etc.</i>
Size of the dataset	<i>approximate number of records: 1000s? millions? more?</i>
Size of the dataset	<i>approximate size in bytes / MB / GB</i>
Restrictions	<i>any restrictions due to AVG/GDPR, copyright, ethical issues, etc.</i>
More information	<i>website, if available</i>

Please confirm that

The dataset will be available at the start of the project

ODISSEI facilities

Indicate which ODISSEI facilities are expected to be used (if any) and how (see 1.3 of the call text). Note that this call does not provide funding for an access to these facilities.

- CBS Microdata access
- LISS panel access
- OSSC Secure Supercomputer time
- ODISSEI Social Data Science Team assistance (does not need funding, subject to availability)
- AS Review

Explanation

Explain how these facilities may be used:

Statement by the applicant

The eScience Center strictly applies the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the EU regulation aimed at strengthening data protection for all individuals within the EU (see www.eugdpr.org). In the Netherlands the regulation is implemented as the 'Algemene Verordening Gegevensbescherming (AVG)'. Applicants are required to follow these rules and regulations, as well as the principles, in as much as these are applicable to the proposed work.

The eScience Center also applies the Code Openness Animal Experiments and the Biosecurity Code of Conduct (available at www.knaw.nl). Applicants must check whether the codes have relevance to their application. If so, the eScience Center requires applicants to endorse the code(s) and act according to these. In case of the Biosecurity Code, the applicant is convinced that the knowledge presented in the application cannot lead to dual use.

Applicants are required to endorse and follow the Netherlands eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and Intellectual Property (available in this application pack and at www.esciencecenter.nl). For alternative IP agreements, contact the eScience Center before proposal submission.

By signing this completed form, I agree to

- endorse and follow the rules and regulations as laid out in AVG, as well as the underlying principles (GDPR).
- endorse and follow the Code Openness Animal Experiments (if applicable).
- endorse and follow the eScience Center Rules towards Publishing, Licensing, and IP.
(If you feel you cannot endorse and follow these rules, then please contact the eScience Center before submitting the proposal. You will be required to justify yourself.)

I have completed this form truthfully.

Name:

Place:

Date: